

Marketing Affects of Noodles by Radio Advertisement on the Consumption of Noodles (Rum Pum) In Nepal

Shailendra Siwakoti

Faculty of Management, T.U.M.M.A.M. Campus, Biratnagar, Nepal.

Abstract

This paper is projected brunt of advertising burning up of noodles in Nepal. Advertising is a part of everyday life for everyone, hence it is difficult to escape them even if we never go through the television program or listen to the FM[Frequency Modulation] radios or read newspaper or magazines. We would still be bombarded with the advertisements through billboards at the highways shopping complex, Bus Park, crossway posters in the shops and offices and pamphlets in the wall. More than that advertising is in the form of the leaflets too. The sponsor is notorious by his company's name or brand name or both. By an aid, the sponsor is not identified and it is not paid for its use of media in which it has appeared then the significance point is considered to be publicity by qualitative and quantitatively study too.

Keywords: Advertisement; Qualitative; Quantative; Crossway; Sponsor.

Introduction

Marketing has been developing together with every other development in human civilization. It covers the very wide area now has not been developed at once. If we go several centuries back to the history of human civilization, we find the contemporary marketing as used today. But the situation has been changed drastically and it has brought a wide change in human needs. Human aspiration for excellence and better status given birth to thousands of discoveries, inventions, innovations and established much more different industries to fulfill that aspiration[Kotler P. & Armstrong G. (2007)]. These changes have invented not only different sophisticated tools and techniques, and effective strategies for successful marketing but also the marketing itself has become a most competitive field. The word advertising is derived from a Latin word 'advertere' which means to turn attention towards specific things. The dictionary meaning of the word advertising is to announce publicly or to give public notice. In earlier time advertising meant merely to inform. Some advertisements today still do just that to provide information about birth, death, engagements with little or no attention to persuade. Advertising is one of the most widely used promotion tools. It is used by business, non-government organizations [Kotler P. & Keller K. (2006)] charities and service institutions. It is one of the major tools that companies use to persuade target buyers and publics to buy their products or services. The main purposes of advertising is to inform the people about product features used etc. and to persuade the people to purchase the product features uses etc. and to persuade the people to purchase the particular product. It is a non-personal form of communication conducted through paid media aimed at a target group. It is a mass communication and is transmitted through the mass media i.e. radio, television, magazines and newspaper. A product, service or idea can be presented and promoted in a variety of ways and among them advertising is one of the most acceptable tools. Advertising influences consumer attitudes and purchase behavior in a variety of consolidated manner. It has multiple objectives and roles in persuading the consumer. The techniques of the advertising may be directed by one or more objectives of advertising depending upon the nature of the product and situation. The main focus of this study is to find out how advertising affects the behavior of the people in buying different types of commodities. Many important decisions have to be made before undertaking the advertising program[Nwaizugbo I.C.(2004)]. It is certainly one of the most important and complex decision facing business executives. Major decision areas in developing advertising program include setting the advertising objectives, deciding on the advertising popular. Human behavior is very complex process. Behavior is the sum of observable human activities. Now two people always behave in the same way. Advertiser must understand the customer's behavior and

must present the advertisement in such a way that persuades the people to buy the particular product. Advertisers must understand how customer select, buy, use and dispose products. They must know customer motivation of consumption of noodles especially RUMPUM by radio advertisement in Nepal [Shimp T.A. (2000)]. This paper describes the affect of radio advertisement of consumption of noodles by people in Nepal.

Methodology

This study attempts to study the impact of Radio advertising toward the buying behavior of consumer. To get this objective the relationship between three independent variables, i.e. consumer attitude perception and credibility towards advertisement which dependent variable consumer buying behavior is analyzed. Besides these prime objectives there are two subsidiary objectives of the study, i.e. to know about the factor that affects consumer buying behavior. It is very hard to choose the research design to best fit to the study without error to achieve. The population of the study comprised all the consumer of Rum Pum noodles in Biratnagar city as well as whole country like Nepal.. Among them 100 respondents were selected as the sample for the study on the basis of convenience including both male and female from different areas of Biratnagar City as well as all over the country. Questionnaire method is followed to collect data and respondents are interviewed when necessary. Consumers of Nepal who are also the viewers of radio are sources of data and attempted by qualitative and quantitative also.

Results and Discussions

From the collected data and their analysis were performed to achieve the objectives which had been mentioned in the introduction chapter. The presentation and analysis of data consisting of organizing, tabulating and analyzing mathematical and statistical result. Different tables and diagrams were drawn to make result simple and easily understandable some table and diagrams had been published by the company itself which were also presented while analyzing data [http://nepalitimes.com/news.php?Id=2409accessedMarch16].

It is a pictorial presentation of data to understand the further analysis at a glance. It is presented here to given idea on the factors affecting buying behavior, consumer attitude and buying pattern. It also helps to understand the general attitude towards advertising. It can prove or disprove the fact by the data presented in graphs, but it help to get insight into the nature and direction of the data. The prime objective of this presentation is to provide the background to understand the next part of the analysis easily to present the factors considered under study and to give an insight in to the nature of the data studies[MaharjanandKabita,2009].

Popular of the Media

There are several types of medias i.e. Television, Radio, Newspaper, Hording board etc. The table below shows the effect of advertisement.

Types of media	No of respondents	Percentage
Television	30	30
Radio	32	32
Newspaper	22	22
Hoarding Board	16	16
Total	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2014

It is found that 30 person (30%) reorganization those advertisement which telecast throw T.V. 32 people (32%) people reacting for those advertisement which is board casting throw the Radio/FM. 22 people (22%) people reacting for the those advertisement which publish in Newspaper and 16 people (16%) get their attention towards hoarding board. These data clearly indicate that most of the people reacting about those produce which advertisement is pass throw F.M./Radio. It means Radio / F.M. is more effective than other media. The effect show in below pie-chart.

Figure 1: Popularity of Media

Consumer Habit of Hearing Radio Advertisement:

It is no meaning of advertisement if consumers have not interest on hearing. Radio advertisement so in this chapter we try to test consumer habit of hearing and hearing Radio Advertisement. The table below presents the consumer habit of hearing advertisement.

Description	Sample Size	Hearing	%	Not hearing	%
Male	50	40	80%	10	20%
Female	50	42	84%	8	16%
Total	100	82		18	

Source: Field Survey, 2014

Living in Biratnagar, out of total sample population 82% of people are found to have the habit of hearing Television advertisement of analyze the figure of male and female. (80% male and 84% female). The percentage of women hearing advertisement seem to higher by 4% like wise (20% male and 16% female) 4% higher male have habit of not hearing advertisement. The statistics is presented below thought multiple bar diagram.

Figure 2: Consumer Habit and Hearing Radio Advertisement

Impact of Advertising on Consumer

It is very important to know that what kind of impact advertisement provides to consumer. Some advertisement creates positive impact among the consumer regarding the advertised product while sometime it creates negative impact. So this survey is for the test. The impact of advertisement and result is presented at table 3.

Table 3: Impact of Advertisement on Consumer			
Descript	No. of Sample	No. of Respond	%
Positive Impact	100	63	63%
No Impact	100	22	22%
Negative impact	100	15	15%
	100	100	100

Source: Field Survey, 2014

The above table shows the impact of advertisement out of 100 sample 63 people (63%) said that the advertisement made their decision easy while purchasing good. They said easily recall those product which has good advertising out of 100 sample 22 people 22% people said they have no impact for advertisement i.e. they purchase those good which they purchase further out of 100 sample 15 people (15%) said they didn't purchase those good which advertise highly. The above result presented in pie-chart below.

Figure 3: Impact of Advertisement on Consumer

Impact of frequency of advertisement:

Frequency of advertisement plays great role to influxes consume consumer friezes different product by considering various factor advertisement is also one of the important factor which affect. The consumer's preference of the particular. They result of the consumer preference to various types of product is presented in the table below.

Figure 4: Impact of Frequency of Advertisement

The above figure clearly shows that the majority of people believe on those advertisement which advertised frequently 81% people says that they appreciate for frequently advertised advertisement and only 19% says that they understand advertisement of one time. The above information nearly shows in pie-chart below.

4.3 Adequacy of Advertisement

Consumer can be receive various useful information regarding the product usefulness or benefits, suing techniques and its effect on their daily life etc. from the advertisement. The situation of consumer's response regarding the adequacy of advertisement is presented below:

Table 5: Adequacy of Advertisement		
Description	No. of respondent	Percentage
See information for additional	78	78%
Adequate information	22	22%
Total	100	100%
Source: Field Survey, 2014		

The above table shows in brief the consumers reaction to the adequacy of the advertisement. Among the total 100 respondent 78% wanted some more information to be added in the advertisement whereas 22% responded that the context of the advertisement are adequate i.e. they are fully satisfied with the information received from advertisement of particular product.

Therefore, from the analysis it can be concluded that noodle it's of consumer are willing to add additional information in the advertisement so that the advertisement would be adequate enough to accomplish the demand of the consumer. The above information clearly shows in pie-chart below

Figure 5: Adequacy of Advertisement

Consumer's Preference to the Product Having Same Price and Quality

The consumer may give different preference to the product having same price and quality due to effect of advertisement. The result of the consumer's preferences towards such product due to the impact of advertisement can be presented as follows:

Table 6: Consumer's Preference to the Product Having Same Price and Quality		
Description	No. of respondent	Percentage
Advertise Product	83	83%
Not advertise product	17	17%
Total	100	100%
Source: Field Survey, 2014		

The above table shows the preference of consumer to the product having same price and quality act of the total 100 respondent 83% given preference to the advertised product whereas 17% given reference to non advertised consumer. The following result is shown in pie-chart below.

Figure 6: Consumer's Preference to the Product Having Same Price and Quality

Age Wise Consumer Preference on Advertisement

The total shows the age level and their advertisement preference the sample size of total people was divided into five groups of 20 people. The detail situation has been presented in below:

Table 7: Age Wise Consumer Preference on Advertisement

Description	Sample size	Musical	Good working	Simple	All type
Below 20	20	12	4	2	2
20-30	20	11	4	4	1
30-40	20	5	8	2	5
40-50	20	3	7	6	4
Above 50	20	1	11	9	0
Total	100	32	33	23	12

Source: Field Survey, 2014

From the above table, it was found that out of 20 people of age group below 20, 12 people preferred musical advertisement 4 people found to prefer good wording, 2 people of below 20 preferred good working and 2 people also prefer all types. The reaction of people those fall in age group 20 to 30, 11 people preferred musical advertisement. 4 people each preferred good wording and simple advertisement and only 1 people preferred all type i.e. musical good wording. Simple which clearly means that majority of age group prefer musical advertisement taking about of age group 30 to 40. 5 people preferred musical advertisement, 8 people preferred good wording. 2 people preferred simple and 5 people preferred all type of advertisement at the age of group of 40 to 50, out of 20 people 3,7,6,4 preferred musical, good wording simple, all types of respectively. It means that majority of people preferred good wording advertisement at the age of group of above 50, only 1 people preferred musical advertisement. 11 people preferred good wording. 9 people preferred simple and zero people preferred all types of advertising the data are clearly show on multiple bar diagram below.

Figure 7: Age Wise Consumer Preference on Advertisement

Literacy Wise Consumer's Preference on Advertisement

The table below shows the literacy level and their advertisement preference. The sample size of total people is divided into five group or respondent in each group. The detail situation has been presented in the following table.

Table 8: Literacy Wise Consumer's Preference on Advertisement

Description	Sample size	Musical	Good working	Simple	All type
Below SLC	20	13	2	1	4
SLC	20	9	4	4	3
Graduate	20	5	9	3	3
Upper Graduate	20	2	7	6	5
Uneducated	20	11	2	2	5
Total	100	32	33	23	12

Source: Field Survey, 2014

The above table shows that lower educated respondents people preferred to musical advertisement regarding musical advertisement 13 people preferred musical advertisement where as 9 people SLC preferred it. Likewise 5 graduate people preferred it 2 upper graduates preferred it and if uneducated people preferred it. Similarly, regarding advertisement with good working, 2 people and 2 uneducated people preferred advertisement with good working, considering simple advertisement 1 below SLC. 4 SLC level, 3 graduate, 6 upper graduate and 2 uneducated people preferred it. And for all types 4, 3, 3, 5, 5 people of below SLC, SLC pass, graduate, upper graduate preferred it. The meaning of that calculation upper graduate and graduate people are more focus about good working. While lower educated people focus on musical advertisement to understand the above information properly the below multiple bar diagram is presented.

Figure 8: Literacy Wise Consumer's Preference on Advertisement

Preference of Advertising According to Gender

The situation of preference of consumer on advertising according to the gender is presented below:

Description	Sample size	Musical	Good working	Simple	All type
Male	50	20	24	5	1
Female	50	22	17	3	6
Total	20	42	41	8	7

Source: Field Survey, 2014

The above table show preference of advertisement according to gender of 50 male, 20 responded are found to like the musical advertisement, 24 respondent preferred good working, 5 respondent preferred simple advertisement and 1 like all type of advertisement. Regarding no female respondents 22 preferred for musical advertisement, 17 good working, 3 simple, 6 all type preferred advertising respectively for more clarity the above information presented with the help of the pie-chart.

Figure 9: Preference of Advertising According to Gender Male

Figure 10: Preference of Advertising According to Gender Female

Age Wise Consumer's Reaction to the Advertisement

The different age group recall to advertisement differently like some of them tries to know what advertisement meant some of them may be uninterested about advertisement, whereas, some just watch or hear advertisement. The situation of consumer reaction according to the age group is presented in table below.

Description	Same size	Try to know	Curious	Just hearing
Below 20	20	7	4	9
20-30	20	11	5	4
30-40	20	5	10	5
40-50	20	9	1	10
Above 50	20	3	10	7
Total	100	35	30	35

Source: Field Survey, 2014

The above statistics shows that the total sample population belonging to different age group does not have the same opinion about advertisement. The result regarding the consumer opinion on advertisement indicate that 7 respondent belongs to trust age group want just to know the literal meaning of advertisement. 4 respondents are really curious about advertisement whereas 9 respondents are passive advertisement audience. Likewise, among the respondent belonging to age group of 20 to 30. 11 respondents are conscious only with the meaning of advertisement 5 are highly inquisitive to the advertisement while 4 responded are more audience. Analyze the third group 30 to 40 out of 20 respondent 5 people are try to know the meaning of advertisement 10 people are curious about advertisement and 5 people are more audient hen other. In the fourth age group out of 20 people 9 are interested on the meaning of advertisement 1 person curious about to advertisement and 10 people are just hearing. In the fifth age group majority of people 10 people are curious about advertisement than after 7 people are just passing their time by hearing advertisement, 3 people are conscious of meaning i.e. they try to know the meaning. The above analysis is more clearly presented in the following chart.

Fig 11: Age Wise Reaction to the Advertisement

Education Wise Reaction to the Advertisement

The reaction to the advertisement according to their education it presented in the table below.

Description	Same Size	Try To Know	Curious	Just Hearing
Below SLC	20	6	2	12
SLC	20	6	8	6
Graduate	20	13	6	1
Upper Graduate	20	9	11	0
Uneducated	20	4	3	13
Total	100	38	30	32

Source: Field Survey, 2014

The above table indicated the reaction of respondents in term of their education status 6 respondent having qualification below SLC opined that they want to know only the meaning of advertisement, 2 out of total 20 respondent are found to be highly interested to the advertisement whereas 12 respondent are found to be more audience.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study, following suggestions or recommendations are recommended:

- They study shows that majority of respondents of different age groups and various educational backgrounds prefer musical backgrounds programs rather than other programs. So, the produce as well as advertisers either makes their advertisement in musical form of they should broadcast the advertisement in musical program.
- They study shows that majority of the respondents have habit of listening radio and it is more popular with women consumers. So, the advertisers and producers should give preference to the radio advertisement by focusing more to the women advertisement.
- The analysis shows that the information included in advertisement are not sufficient and majority of the respondents are willing to get the additional information from the advertisement regarding various aspects of the product. Thus, advertisers, manufactures and producers should include sufficient information so that consumer can be satisfied regarding the matter.
- They study indicates that the advertisement of any product leaves the good impact to consumer behavior regarding the product but to some extent their purchasing depends upon the need of the consumers.
- So the manufacturers and advertisers should also try to create the necessity of the product through advertisement using effective presentation of product, and product related information in their advertisement.
- The advertisement of noodles product is very much effective to leave a positive impact upon consumer regarding the product rather than other variables. So, all the manufacturers of noodles product should produce a product having good quality and advertise their product effectively such that their market share increases rapidly.
- They study indicates that the Rum Pum instant noodles are more popular product than other noodles product. So, the firm should try to maintain this strength in future too. In the study, majority of the respondents stated that the price of Rum Pum is comparatively higher than other noodles product.
- So, the producer of Rum Pum instant noodles should address this weakness and the price of the product should be comparatively reasonable as other competitive product.

Conclusions

From above discussion based on data it is obviously that this study has revealed advertising as a primary tool in the marketing decision variables of a firm and effective in the marketing of consumer products, Rum Pum noodles in particular. Therefore, the answer to the question, "can advertising be evaluated" is unreservedly yes. Every marketing

variable of any business concern must be evaluated in terms of the contribution it makes to the growth of the business. By virtue of this study, it has been discovered that advertising shapes a consumer's perception about a product. As the business environment is becoming more challenging and risky, business organizations are failing as a result of poor decisions and low patronage, it's no doubt therefore, to say that advertising could help increase the demand for a product by making it popular in the minds of the consumers. According to the findings of the analysis section it can be concluded that majority of the people have habits of listening radio and out of them, women are more curious in listening radio than men which indicates that radio advertisement is more popular means of advertisement than all other types of advertisement but most of them just listen rather than to know any new information. In addition to this majority of the people of differing are group as well as different educational class and gender prefers to the musical programs as compared to other types of radio programs which indicates that musical programs are more popular among the people than other programs. Similarly, majority of the people prefers the product which is frequently advertised rather than non-advertised products though the products are of similar nature. But most of them purchase the product due to their necessity and not due to the influence of advertisement. Likewise, the advertisement of noodles product like Rum Pum is very much effective to make the customer familiar about the product but majority of them are influenced by the equality of product and not by the advertisement though they know about that product from advertisement. Thus, in conclusion it can be concluded that radio advertisement seems to be the most popular means or media which plays crucial role to enhance the market of the goods manufactured.

References:

- [1] Kotler P. & Armstrong G. (2007) Principles of Marketing, 12th Ed: New Delhi:Prentice Hall of India.
- [2] Kotler P. & Keller K. (2006) Marketing Management, 12th Ed: Upper.
- [3] Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [4] Nwaizugbo I.C. (2004) Principles of Marketing: Enugu, Nigeria:New generation books.
- [5] Shimp T.A. (2000) Advertising & Promotion, 5th Ed: SouthCarolina, USA: the Dryden Press Chapter two
Kaushik,JayShankar,ManishNarangandAnkitParakh,2011,FastFoodConsumptioninChildren,Journalof
IndianPediatricsVolume48,NewDelhi,India.
- [6] .Maharjanand Kabita,2009, Knowledge&consumption at tern of junk food among adolescents at Katmandu & metropolitan city & Kirtipur municipality , an unpublished MA dissert at ion submitted to Home , Tribhuvan University .Naya Patrika2013, Junk food rumors in school(translatedfromNepali),Editorial news Kathmanu
- [7] Uprety,DrAruna,2012,Junkfoodepidemic,available
<http://nepalitimes.com/news.php?Id=2409>accessedMarch16,2013.